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GREEN CLOUD COMPUTING

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❖ Abstract :

Currently, cloud computing is one of the most in-demand technologies which gives any organization a fresh look by offering virtualized services on demand. Every organization, from small to medium sized and large, uses cloud computing services to store information and allow access to it 24/7 via the internet from any location.

The development of new features and techniques for cloud computing systems that have a great capacity for delivering more sophisticated cloud solutions is being aided by recent research on other significant limits. Cloud based data centers, platforms, servers and the other infrastructure services are enough elastic to supply the sudden demand of huge resources from customers.

These services can also further increase the internet traffic and its growing information database which could decrease such energy savings. Most of the issues that modern corporate organization's faces are being addressed by clouds, but they are suffering from few notable limitations like huge power consumption, more CPU idle times, need of deploying the resources at upper bound, emission of carbon gases and producing huge electronic waste (e-waste) material.

Therefore, creating a cloud environment that is eco-friendly, like "Green Cloud Computing," is necessary today. Businesses have adopted green cloud computing to protect the environment. Let's find out, what green cloud computing is?, why it's so popular?, its advantages and disadvantages, and the businesses using the greenest clouds.

❖ Key Words :

Green Cloud Computing, Cloud computing, Virtualization, Energy efficiency, Environmental protection, Multitenancy, Sustainability.

❖ Introduction :

Green cloud computing is used not only to achieve efficient processing and use of computing infrastructure, but also to minimize energy consumption. Also known as GREEN IT. Over the past decade, cloud computing has become a popular computing platform for business organizations, helping entrepreneurs focus on core business operations instead of wasting time and money on infrastructure management. It offers various services like IaaS, PaaS and SaaS to attract the business applications owners to adopt and migrate the cloud services to their business app modules as presented in below figure.

Cloud based data centers, platforms, servers and the other infrastructure services are enough elastic to supply the sudden demand of huge resources from customers. Green cloud computing reduces the use of hazardous material which causes harm to environment. It offers a detailed fine-grained modeling of the energy consumed by the data center IT equipment, such as computing servers, network switches and communication links.

Therefore, today's cloud environment should be developed as environmentally friendly as "Green Cloud Computing". While cloud computing in general focuses primarily on efficient storage and processing of data, the term Green Cloud Computing refers to cloud computing that was introduced with the main goal of making the cloud environment greener.

❖ Architecture of Green Cloud Computing :

Green Cloud Architecture (GCA) is an IDC architecture aimed at reducing datacenter power consumption. The advantage of this architecture is to guarantee real-time performance while saving the overall power consumption of the IDC.

In this, users submit their Cloud service requests through a new middleware Green Broker that manages the selection of the greenest Cloud provider to serve the user's request. A green request can be of three types i.e. software, platform or infrastructure. The Cloud providers can register their services in the form of "green offers" to a public directory which is accessed by Green Broker. The green offers consist of green services, pricing and time when it should be accessed for least carbon emission. Green Broker gets the current status of energy parameters for using various Cloud services from Carbon Emission Directory. The Carbon Emission Directory maintains all the data related to energy efficiency of Cloud service. This data may include PUE (Power Usage Effectiveness) and cooling efficiency of Cloud datacenter which is providing the service, the network cost and carbon emission rate of electricity, Green Broker calculates the carbon emission of all the Cloud providers who are offering the requested Cloud service. Then, it selects the set of services that will result in least carbon emission and buy these services on behalf of users.

The Green Cloud framework is designed to make their service clean by keeping track of overall energy usage of serving a user request. It relies on two main components, Carbon Emission Directory and Green Cloud offers. A user can use Cloud to access any of these three types of services (SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS), and therefore process of serving them should also be energy efficient. In other words, from the Cloud provider side, each Cloud layer needs to be "Green" conscious.

SaaS Level (Software as a Service) :

Since SaaS providers mainly offer software installed on their own datacenters or resources from IaaS providers, the SaaS providers need to model and measure energy efficiency of their software design, implementation, and deployment. For serving users, the SaaS provider chooses the datacenters which are not only energy efficient but also near to users.

PaaS level (Platform as a Service) :

PaaS providers offer in general the platform services for application development. The platform facilitates the development of applications which ensures system wide energy efficiency. Platforms itself can be designed to have various code level optimizations which can cooperate with underlying compiler in energy efficient execution of applications.

IaaS level (Infrastructure as a Service) :

Providers in this layer plays most crucial role in the success of whole Green Architecture. They use latest technologies for IT and cooling systems to have most energyefficient infrastructure. By using virtualization and consolidation, the energy consumption is further reduced by switching-off unutilized server. Various energy meters and sensors are installed to calculate the current energy efficiency of each IaaS providers and their sites. This information is advertised regularly by Cloud providers in Carbon Emission Directory. The Cloud provider designs various green offers and pricing schemes for providing incentive to users to use their services during off-peak or maximum energy- efficiency hours.

Green cloud architecture is the result of these processes leading to both energy efficiency and a conscious understanding of carbon emissions. The purpose of building green spaces is to reduce energy consumption. ICT industry, more than any other, is responsible for a significant part of worldwide energy growth. Green cloud computing aims to encourage their cycling or biodegradability of outmoded items and industry waste by decreasing the usage of hazardous compounds and enhancing energy efficiency throughout the product life cycle.

The goal is to reduce power consumption in data centers. It has ideal features such as online monitoring, virtual machine migration and visibility placement. This green cloud architecture structure can help you save up to 27%. Having to manage multiple applications in your data center makes it difficult to provision the necessary resources and allocate them to different workloads. To guarantee performance and maintain segmentation, domain data resources have statistical applications that rely on loaders.

The main characteristics of the Green Cloud are energy efficiency, virtualization, multi-tenancy (high-end usability), consolidation, automation, resilience, reusability, and sustainability of cloud resources. World's green nature must not be affected by the naïve innovations like cloud computing, henceforth the experts are strongly recommending that the "Cloud Computing" must consider the ecology gaining along with economy".

❖ Pros & Cons of Green Cloud Computing :

- Pros:
 - Conserving Energy by Green Cloud Computing.
 - Remote Working reduces the Carbon Footprint in the Environment.
 - Going Paperless with Green Computing and Cloud Computing.
 - Reduction in E-waste Generation.

- Cons:
 - Implementation Cost is High.
 - Evolving Technology will be challenging to Adapt.
 - Green Computers may be considered Underpowered.

❖ Conclusion :

The goal of green cloud architecture is to reduce data center power consumption. The main advantage of green cloud computing architecture is to reduce the energy consumption of IDC (Internet Data Center) while guaranteeing real-time performance. The concept of “Going Green” has existed since 1992. Despite its drawbacks, Green Cloud Computing is a term being studied to protect the environment. It will continue to change and evolve but is essential to reduce carbon emissions into the environment. The idea is to save money and protect the environment in long term goal.

The risk to human life from disposing of e-waste is also expected to be significantly reduced. Combining cloud computing and green computing can help companies to create a productive work environment while reducing their carbon emissions.

Green Cloud Computing and environmental sustainability are important today.

Amazon Web Services, Microsoft and Google have all taken steps to reduce the carbon footprints of their hundreds of data centers worldwide. Each has expressed a commitment to sustainability, clean energy and energy efficiency.

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